

International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management (IJMFM)

ISSN: 2348 –3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –2546 (Print)

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A STUDY OF THE PERCEPTION OF INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS TOWARDS INVESTMENT IN MUTUAL FUNDS WHEN COMPARED TO OTHER ALTERNATIVES

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Abstract

The research report is based on the study made on the comparative analysis of the Mutual fund and other alternative investment options which were the study made for 8 weeks duration from 10th April 2014 to 9th June 2014. The main purpose of doing this project was to know about mutual fund and its functioning. This helps to know in details about mutual fund industry right from its inception stage, growth and future prospects. It also helps in understanding different schemes of mutual funds. My study depends upon prominent funds in India and their schemes like equity, income, balance as well as the returns associated with those schemes. Ultimately this would help in understanding the benefits of mutual funds to investors and also alternate investment options like the mutual funds which can be Options, Futures, FOREX, Gold, Real Estate. This report is presented in terms of various chapters such as the Design of the study, Introduction, Data analysis and Interpretation Summary of findings, Recommendations and Conclusion. In the design of the study, the areas covered are highlighted in terms of introduction, objective scope, methodology, limitations and review of literature. The main objective is to know the preference made by the investors towards the mutual fund is more or they go into the other alternate investment options like fixed deposits, savings account of bank, options, futures, FOREX, gold, real estate. The study involves the mutual fund industry profile and its history and its categories as well its investment strategies. It also covers the overview of existing schemes existed in mutual fund category. The study also tells the advantages as well as the disadvantages in mutual fund schemes when compared to other alternate investment options.

Most of the investors are aware of the mutual funds but they don't know the benefits derived from it so it is important for them to be understood. Mutual is not so popular as in the case of the foreign countries. Mutual funds are also growing in the country but it and its advantages are not known by everyone. This project undertaken deals with customer perception with regard to mutual funds that is the investments they prefer, the reasons behind such selections and also this project dealt with different investment options, which people prefer along with and apart from mutual funds. The findings from this project is that most of the people are hesitant in going for new age investments like mutual funds and prefer to avert risks by investing in less riskier investment options like other deposits and so.

Key words: Mutual funds, Alternative Investments, Bank, Risk

Introduction:

A research design is a systematic plan to study a scientific problem. The design of a study defines the study type (descriptive, correlational, semi-experimental, experimental, review, meta-analytic) and sub-type (e.g., descriptive-longitudinal case study), research question, hypotheses, independent and dependent variables, experimental design, and, if applicable, data collection methods and a statistical analysis plan. The research design refers to the overall strategy that you choose to integrate the different components of the study in a coherent and logical way, thereby, ensuring you will effectively address the research problem; it constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement, and analysis of data.

The research study can be of two types - Qualitative approach which involves the collection of extensive narrative data in order to gain insights into phenomena of interest. Here the data analysis includes the coding of the data and production of the verbal. It includes historical research and qualitative research. Qualitative approach involves the collection of numerical data in order to explain, predict and/or control phenomena of interest. Here the data analysis is mainly statistical. It includes descriptive research, correlation research casual-comparative research and experimental with the Indian mutual fund industry, how is it growing its comparative analysis with the alternate investment options preferred by the investors. Mutual fund is a trust that pools the savings of a number of investors who share a common financial goal. This pool of money is invested in accordance with the stated objective. The joint ownership of the fund is thus “mutual”, i.e. the fund belongs to all the investors. Here the study shows that the Mutual fund is an investment tool that allows small investors access to a well –diversified portfolio of equities, bonds and other securities when compared to the other alternate investment like gold, real estate, options, futures etc.

Objectives of the Study:

- To know the purpose and performance and of investment in mutual fund.
- To know the purpose and performance and of investment in other investment.
- To study the behaviour of Indian individual investors towards the investment of their savings.
- To study the perception of Indian individual investors towards the investment in mutual funds when compared to other alternatives.

Need for the Research:

The research is conducted to find the comparative analysis of the mutual fund and other alternative investment options and how the people prefer the investments based on the benefits they derive. The study is to know the how intensively awareness about mutual fund has been created among investors.

Scope of the Study:

The study of comparative analysis of the mutual fund and other alternative investment options helps us to know how the investors react keeping in mind the benefits they derive. The study covers age groups of ranging from 20 years to 55 years and their responses towards the Mutual funds. The sample size we considered for the study was 100 and regions covered for the study is some parts of city of Bangalore. This particular study is conducted during the month April 2014 to June 2014 and does not represent whole nation.

Methodology:

The research is carried out through primary data and secondary data. Structured questionnaire is used to collect primary data from 100 respondents of age group ranging from 20 years to 55 years with no discretion of gender. The respondents are selected on convenience method in Bangalore. Secondary data are already available information,

collected for other purposes. The required information are collected through websites, journals, magazines and newspaper of national circulation.

Review of Literature:

Singh and Singla (2000) evaluated the performance of twelve growth oriented mutual funds for October 1992 to September 1996. They used Treynor index, Sharpe index and Jensen measure and concluded that mutual funds did not perform better than their benchmark indicators. Also, **Chander (2000)** measured the performance of selected Indian mutual fund schemes by using Sharpe measure, Treynor measure and Jensen differential measure. In their study, it was found that majority of sample mutual funds showed superior performance as compared to their benchmark portfolio.

Parihar et al. (2009) analysed the impact of different demographic variables on the attitude of investors towards mutual funds and surveyed 200 respondents of Agra region. Their study revealed that the majority of investors had not formed any attitude towards mutual funds for investments mainly because of the lack of awareness. They also found that respondent’s age, gender and income were significantly associated with their attitude towards mutual funds whereas their education and occupation were not associated with the same. Factors due to which investors invested in mutual funds were their return potential, liquidity, flexibility, affordability and transparency.

Sikidar & Singh et al. (1996) studied the behavioural aspect of investors of the North Eastern region towards equity and mutual funds investment portfolio. They found that salaried and self employed were the major investors of mutual funds. Also UTI and SBI mutual fund schemes were the most popular in that part of the country.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

1. Age and Occupation of respondents:

Table No. 1: Age * Occupation Cross tabulation

		Occupation				Total
		Gov.sec	Pvt.sec	Business	Agriculture	
Age	20-24	1	3	0	0	4
	25-29	5	9	3	2	19
	30-34	7	9	6	4	26
	35-49	8	8	9	3	28
	50-55	5	7	9	2	23
Total		26	36	27	11	100

Source: Field Survey

Interpretation: In my survey I have respondents belonging to the age group from 20-55 years. Based on their occupation I have categorized them in the following way. They are categorized based on the field they are in like private, government, business and agriculture.

2. Age and income of respondents:

Table No. 2: Age * income Cross tabulation

		Income			
		50000-100000	100000-500000	500000 & more	Total
Age	20-24	15	9	0	24
	25-29	10	7	6	23
	30-34	2	8	12	22
	35-49	1	9	7	17
	50-55	0	8	6	14
Total		28	41	31	100

Source: Field Survey

Interpretation: In the following chart the age group from 20-55 are categorised based on their annual income. The income earnings below 100000 is more among the respondents when compared to others who mainly come under 20-24 age group.

3. Type of investments made:

Table No. 3: Type of investments made

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Savings account	32	32
	Fixed deposits	22	22
	Insurance	8	8
	Mutual fund	3	3
	Post office-NSC	6	6
	Shares and debentures	9	9
	Gold/silver	10	10
	Real estate	10	10

Source: Field Survey

Interpretation: Among the respondents the main investments made by them are on the savings account following the fixed deposits which are mainly the bank accounts. Then their investments are on the gold, real estates. When compared to this the investments in insurance, post office schemes is relatively less and mutual fund is the least.

4. Factors considered for investment:

Table No. 4: Factors considered for investment

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Liquidity	26	26
	Low risk	14	14
	High return	50	50
	Trust	10	10

Source: Field Survey

Interpretation: Among the respondents the main factor considered for investment is the return that they are willing to earn on their investments that is 50 percent of them. And the next thing is to be considered is the liquidity they want on their investments and then the trust and the low risk.

5. Awareness on MF's:

Table No. 5: Awareness on MF's

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Yes	78	78
	No	22	22
	Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey

Interpretation: Among the respondents I surveyed 78 percent of them are aware of mutual funds and 22 percent are not aware of it.

6. Awareness through different sources:

Table No. 6: Awareness through different sources

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Advertisement	25	25
	Peer group	35	35
	Banks	25	25
	Financial advisors	15	15
	Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey

Interpretation: Among the respondents most of the awareness are created among them are by the peer groups that is 35 percent of them agree and next through banks and advertisement and comparatively less through financial advisors.

7. Investment in MF's made by respondents:

Table No. 7: Investment in MF's

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Yes	20	20
	No	80	80
	Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey

Interpretation: Among the respondents 80 percent have not invested in the mutual funds and only 20 percent of them have the interest in investing in mutual funds.

8. Reason for not investing in other investments other than MF's:

Table No. 8: Reason for not investing in other investments other than MF's

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Not liquid	10	10
	Not reliable	10	10
	Less returns	65	65
	More risk	25	25
	Total	100	100

Interpretation: Among the respondents who are interested in investing in the mutual funds agree that the other alternatives yield less returns. Its about 65 percent who agree this.

Then about 25 percent who are interested in investing in mutual funds agree that others are more risky and then other respondents agree with that they are not reliable and not liquid.

9. Factors that prevent to invest in MF's compared to other alternatives:

Table No. 9: Factors that prevent to invest in MF's

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Bitter past experience	5	5
Lack of knowledge	40	40
Lack of confidence in service being provided	20	20
Inefficient investment advisors	35	35
Total	100	100

Source: Field survey

Interpretation: Among the respondents about 40 percent of them agree that because of lack of knowledge they are prevented from investing on it and about 35 percent of them because of inefficient investment advisors and others because of bitter past experience and lack of confidence in service.

10. Risk associated with MF's:

Table No. 10: Risk associated with MF's

Valid Low	10	10
Moderate	30	30
High	60	60
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey

Interpretation: Among the respondents about 60 percent of them agree that the risk is more and about 30 percent agree that it is moderate and others agree that risk is less.

11. Risk associated with other investments:

Table No. 11: Risk associated with other investments

Valid Low	40	40
Moderate	40	40
High	20	20
Total	100	100

Source: Field survey

Interpretation: Among the respondents about 40 percent of them agree that the risk is high in other investments and other 40 percent agree that risk is moderate and the rest agree that it is high.

3.12 Expected returns:

Table No. 3.12: Expected returns (%)

Valid 15-10	5	5
10-15	5	5
15-20	10	10
Above 20	80	80
	100	100

Source: Field Survey

Interpretation: Among the respondents about 80 percent of them agree that they expect a return of above 20 and 10 percent agree that expected return shall be between 15-20 percent and next 5 percent of them with 10-15 percent and next 5 with the return of 5-10 percent.

Summary of Findings and Recommendations:

The most vital problem spotted is of ignorance. Investors should be aware of the benefits of the mutual funds. Nobody will invest until and unless he is fully convinced. Investors should be made to realize that ignorance is no longer bliss and what they are losing by not investing. Mutual offer a lot of benefit which no other single option could offer. But most of the people are not even aware of what actually a mutual fund is? They only see it as just another investment option. So the advisors should try to change their mindsets. The advisors should target for more and more young investors. Young investors as well as persons at the height of their career would like to go for advisors due to lack of expertise and time.

Mutual Fund Company needs to give the training of the individual financial advisors about the fund/scheme and its objective, because they are the main source to influence the investors. Before making any investment financial advisors should first enquire about the risk tolerance of the investors/customers, their need and time (how long they want to invest). By considering these three things they can take the customers into consideration. Younger people aged under 35 will be the key new customer group into the future, so making greater efforts with younger customers who show some interest in investing should pay off.

In the study of mine most of the investors are into the savings account and they are not aware of the mutual funds so it is necessary to make them understand the benefits they get from the investment in the mutual fund. They think that the risk associated with the mutual fund is more compared to the other alternate investments. So financial advisors should be the key to tell the importance of the mutual funds. They should make the investors to understand what the mutual fund is. Most of the investors are aware of the mutual funds but they don't know the benefits derived from it so it is important for them to be understood. Mutual is not so popular as in the case of the foreign countries. Mutual funds are also growing in the country but it and its advantages are not known by everyone.

Systematic investment plan (SIP) can be one of the innovative products launched by the asset management companies very recently in the industry. SIP is easy for monthly salaried person as it provides the facility of do the investment in EMI. Most of the investors are not aware of this. So it is necessary for the investors to understand the importance of mutual funds and invest on it.

Conclusion:

The main objectives of rational investors are maximizing returns and minimizing risk, safety of the principal, tradability and liquidity are his subsidiary objectives. For the purpose of investment of saving the investor are having options to invest money in mutual funds and other financial instruments like equity shares, debentures, bonds, warrant, bank deposits. A common investor, who invests their savings into the different assets, is not very much aware about the mutual funds. Financial markets are constantly becoming more efficient by providing more promising solutions to the investors. Investors prefer liquidity and return as an important criteria for investment consideration. Hence mutual fund can be considered as good investment along with other alternatives.

So it is important for every investor to know what is important to them according to their investment and secure good return for their input. So that the investments like mutual funds can become one of the best investments and also it can help in the development of the economy of the country.

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